

Research Article

The Car Conundrum: Examining Car-centered Suburbia and its Relationship to Personal Freedom in New Jersey

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The purpose of this study is to understand the relationship between ideals of American consumer capitalism that manifests in car ownership, car dependency, and the distinct lack of accessibility and usage of public transportation. This study uses a case study approach in collecting a survey from car drivers within a suburban township in NJ. The survey was designed to infer individuals' opinions about car ownership and to understand common transportation practices of daily commutes. Findings across all questions and respondents indicated that individuals enjoyed the freedom that owning a car provides and felt that driving is the only viable option for transportation in this specific area. This conclusion brings attention to inefficiencies in our infrastructure and the necessity for working toward a more sustainable solution to car dependency which individuals can shift their beliefs into adapting.

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In the United States, city planning varies depending on factors such as location, era of construction, and local culture of different regions (Pallagst, et al. 2021). New York is known for its grid-like walkable streets in Manhattan and relatively efficient public transportation, while cities such as Houston have a plethora of multi-lane highways, almost demanding its residents to own a car. The United States has seen trends of city planning based on consumer choices, particularly regarding the market's demands for individual property, as opposed to societal or environmental benefits of community-based living (Pallagst, et al. 2021). This culture of city planning caused urban spaces to be more individualistic, less spatially efficient, and dominated overwhelmingly by cars, with priority for vehicle accessibility outweighing the desire for walkability or adequate public transportation, especially until the 1980s as modern design interventions began to tackle this (Loorbach 2022, Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021). Despite these efforts, automobile-centric infrastructure remains persistent in urban and suburban areas of the United States (Soliz 2021, Talal et. al. 2022).

Most people in the United States have access to at least one vehicle, with driving being the preferred method of travel for the majority of Americans, according to a 2022 survey published by the World Economic Forum (*Cars still dominate the American commute*, 2022). Though public transit may seem unfavorable or costly, owning and operating a car is significantly more expensive. Most obvious is the current gas pricing crisis, hitting people where it hurts - their pockets. Besides gasoline, car insurance and general repair and upkeep add up considerably, not to mention time lost by sitting in traffic. Despite all of this, Americans tend to prefer owning and operating their own vehicles due to the individual freedom it provides.

Spatial planning in the United States influences people of varying socioeconomic backgrounds in different ways. Public works efforts to increase pedestrian safety, such as safer sidewalks and lower speed limits in residential areas and schools, vary greatly across different communities. This variation results in higher rates of unaddressed pedestrian safety issues in lower-income, non-white communities (Chia-Yuan et al. 2022). Furthermore, the concept of Nimbyism, or "Not In My Back Yard-ism" (Pallagst, et al. 2021) that is common within American culture often prevents progressive development that addresses and changes these problems. This ideology is based on individualism and a lack of support for communal living, resulting in Americans not wanting solutions to their problems to come at the cost of their proverbial 'Backyard'. In the case of this study, the 'Backyard' would be most akin to the desire for owning a car.

The way we build our cities and towns affects the economy and environment. U.S. urban centers are expanding, becoming more populated, and in turn becoming more filled with cars (Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021). The European Environmental Agency has determined that human activity has been the largest factor of global warming (Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021), and this can largely be attributed to carbon emissions from excessive car use in cities. The environmental impacts of a car-dependent society present problems that are being felt and will continue to be felt by not just the entire country, but the entire world.

Numerous completed and ongoing studies address the myriad of socioeconomic and environmental problems caused by car-based infrastructure (Pallagst et. al. 2021, Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021, Soliz 2021, Talal et. al. 2022). However, there continues to be a lack of widespread understanding as to *why* this type of urban and suburban development is so prevalent in

the United States as opposed to infrastructure which could rely on public transportation and walkability.

The purpose of this study is to understand the relationship between ideals of American consumer capitalism that manifests in car ownership, car dependency, and the distinct lack of accessibility and usage of public transportation nationwide, through the a case study of a suburban township in New Jersey, in order to call attention to inefficiencies in our infrastructure and to work toward a more sustainable solution, and to perhaps encourage more individuals to utilize and embrace walking, cycling, and public transit. This study addresses the following questions:

1. Do individuals' attitudes toward car ownership reflect the environment and infrastructure around them?
2. How do suburban infrastructure patterns necessitate use of consumer automobiles?

Conceptual Framework

This study aims to bridge the gap between our current understanding of American cultural beliefs and patterns of urban development across the nation. Existing research related to this topic is mainly focused on the effects of infrastructure patterns and not the root causes. However, these studies highlight inefficiencies in American city planning which can be reasonably compared to existing research on market patterns and consumer culture. Through these studies we can see a definite “city planning culture” and can define the United States’ planning culture as one based in capitalistic individualism. Besides city planning culture, this study will also define and address concepts of Automobility, Public Transit, and Consumer Car Culture.

City Planning Culture

Existing studies define “planning culture” as “general beliefs and unconscious or taken-for-granted assumptions that affect planning” (Pallagst et. al. 2021). City planning manifests differently across societies and varying populations, and these differences can be defined as planning cultures. Based on Pallagst et. al. 2021, city planning cultures are not uniform. They differ, based on the countries, social cultures, ideologies, and histories that exist wherever infrastructure is built.

Planning culture can be both intentional and unintentional in terms of the consequences in development. For example, Suburbs were culturally developed to be less congested than urban cities, but the planning culture of them led to car-dependency which causes congested roadways, to the degree that “All dimensions of suburban form and dynamics are impacted by heavy reliance on the car” (Filion 2018).

This dependency on cars as outlined in Filion (2018) is the dominant planning culture across the United States (Pallagst et. al. 2021), and thus will be the definition of U.S. planning culture as referenced in this study.

Automobility and Car-dependent Design

The resulting phenomenon of car-based city planning is often referred to as Automobility (Dovey et. al. 2017, Pallagst et. al. 2021, Salvino et. al. 2018). Automobility as a whole may refer to the sociocultural effects of the automobile on a societal landscape, however studies including Talal, et. al. (2022) characterize Automobility as the practical causes and effects of car-dependency. Car-dependent design breeds landscapes and urban spaces that are unsustainable. In contrast, sustainable cities are generally defined by prioritizing walkability, cycling, public transportation, and high-density housing. (Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021, Soliz 2021, Talal et. al. 2022). This collection of studies all originate from the same Journal, *Sustainability*, highlighting the expertise and relevance of these definitions.

Suburban sprawl and “highway cities” are environmentally unfriendly, extremely costly, and dangerous for pedestrians - these characteristics are synonymous with the concept of Automobility. Automobility has affected how cities have been planned and built over time, with cities built before the emergence of cars being much more friendly to pedestrians (Bass & Livingston 2019). As time has gone on, particularly in the United States, car-dependent cities and infrastructure have become astoundingly more common through urban sprawl (Hatami & Thill, 2022). According to Chartonidou (2022), cities planned around Automobility are visually disturbing and ugly. Unappealing development affects societal progression and personal happiness (Loorbach 2022). Automobility and the prioritization of cars on the road not just affects pedestrians but also bikers (Salvino, et. al. 2018, Soliz, et. al. 2021). Cycling infrastructure such as dedicated and maintained bike lanes, as well as resources for bike sharing are essentially non-existent, or at best very poor, outside of major cities and some college towns, which makes cycling both difficult and dangerous in most parts of the country (McNally et. al., 2023). Studies suggest a positive correlation between bike sharing and public transit use (Zhang & Zhang, 2018). As such, with bike sharing being limited due to Automobility, it can be assumed that public transit is also quite limited - and in fact, it is.

For the purpose of this study, the concept of Automobility will pull from these different definitions and be defined as the tangible and present result of car-based infrastructure planning. This idea is the most prevalent thread across all previously mentioned definitions and serves the goals of this study both simply and effectively.

The Fear of Public Transit

Public transportation is widely regarded and defined among scholars as a less favorable mode of transport for Americans, largely due to personal attitudes surrounding “restrict[ing] travel freedom” (Zhang & Zhang, 2018). Public transportation is relatively poor across the nation as a service, such as a distinct lack of high-speed rail and mass-transit bus systems (Dovey et. al. 2017). Stigmas exist within the United States that dismiss public transportation as less desirable, synonymous with being lower-class, and overall a worse choice than driving (Salvino et. al. 2018).

Public transit stigmas are most vividly defined through the statistics of daily commuting patterns: According to Zhang & Zhang (2018), 76% of Americans drive alone to work every day, while only 5% regularly take public transportation. This lack of commuters on public systems detrimentally affects the operating costs of such systems, as there are simply not enough people

paying fares to cover the cost (Guerra & Cervero, 2011), which makes upkeep and improvement less of a priority for state Departments of Transportation or for private companies offering bus and rail services (Guerra & Cervero, 2011).

After considering this data, for the purpose of this study, Public Transit is synonymous with commuters' less favorable choices. There is a definite stigma and unfavorability assigned to public transit which is highlighted by other studies and will be expanded upon throughout the course of this study.

Consumerism and Car Culture

Consumer culture consists of market patterns, purchase trends, and cultural views of property ownership. One of the most common and desired forms of property ownership in the United States is vehicle ownership, and this overwhelming presence of vehicle owners in America can be defined as car culture. Car culture has drastic effects on transportation, as one study by Zhang & Zhang aptly states, "Vehicle ownership is the dominant factor affecting travel mode choice, and households with more cars have a substantially higher probability of driving and a lower probability of walking, cycling, or using public transit" (Zhang & Zhang, 2018). Car culture is highly connected to the free market and capitalistic framework of the United States.

According to Pallagst et. al. (2021), Market patterns dictate city planning in the United States. Market patterns include supply chain and local industry, as well as cultural product demands. This creates socioeconomic inequalities because consumer choices are not regulated by any sort of governing body, and thus are highly volatile, uneven, and susceptible to becoming exploitative. Capitalistic and individualistic ideology push aside poverty. A study by Chia-Yuan, et. al. (2022), argues that car dependent design perpetuates racial and socioeconomic divides by marginalizing poverty.

Consumer culture, individualism, and beliefs of the "American Dream" directly affect how we build our cities and roads, marginalizing poorer classes and tormenting the environment. For the purpose of this study, Consumer Car Culture will be defined as a social ideology across Americans that emphasizes and encourages a pride in ownership of property, specifically cars.

How Concepts are Related

The concepts described in this framework all correlate. Automobility is reflected in the Planning Culture of the United States, causing a disdain for Public Transit amongst Americans and perpetuating Car Culture. With these concepts defined, this study now aims to identify the deeper relationship between the sociological factors of Car Culture and consumerism and the infrastructure in a local setting, specifically whether the beliefs of individuals in a certain area play a direct role into the tangible results of Planning Culture around them. Understanding these definitions will allow us to define the relationships expressed in the research questions.

Methods

I am interested in qualitative stories about individuals' experiences and beliefs in relation to the 'built environment' (Hatami & Thill 2022) surrounding them. As outlined in the Conceptual Framework, Automobility presents a built environment that affects how people think, feel, and act, and in turn people's actions go on to affect their built environment, or in other words, the infrastructure resulting from their Planning Culture. Rather than collecting documents or statistics, I aimed to capture individual opinions on car ownership, public transportation, walkability, and infrastructure, and used these ideas to infer an understanding of why American automobility is so prevalent.

Sources of Data

The primary source of data for this case study will be individuals' stories in Edison, New Jersey, as this township possesses many of the characteristics defined as Automobility in the Conceptual Framework, including car-dependent zoning with poor walkability. Utilizing interviews, in the form of surveys, will be the best method of answering the research questions. This is because surveys, as a form of interview, capture the "human element" as described in "The Craft of Research" (Booth et. al. 2016), which is imperative to understanding a relationship between infrastructure patterns and opinions on car-dependency. As a survey, these "interviews" are highly structured and standardized, according to the definitions in Merriam (2009). The purpose of this is to allow a larger number of responses with many questions, through a more viable medium than a semi structured, in-person interview.

Utilizing documents or observations would not be as helpful as surveys at addressing the research questions. This is because they tell a different side of the story than what I am attempting to capture. Maps and records from city hall may be useful in contextualizing the area's infrastructure and planning, and observing traffic patterns could be beneficial to understand how people interact with these patterns; however, dedicated observational research is outside the scope of my study. Instead, by asking people on a wide scale about their opinions, I have data that helps me understand the relationship between people's ideologies and the infrastructure present in this area.

Individual people each hold varying opinions about car ownership, public transportation, traffic, road development, and infrastructure. Although it is possible that these planning concepts are not common thoughts amongst most individuals, through living in the environment, it is more than likely that people hold underlying opinions and ideologies about the patterns around them, according to the planning cultures described in Pallagst, et. al. (2021). Edison, NJ is the target space as it holds a special place as a sprawling suburban hub for surrounding towns such as Metuchen and South Plainfield, situated within the outskirts of the New York City metropolitan area, filled with small roads, highways, dense housing, and spatially inefficient development - both aligning and contrasting characteristics of Sustainable city planning (Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021, Soliz 2021, Talal et. al. 2021). Edison encompasses different Planning Cultures in one town, as well as being local to me as a student researcher, making research much more accessible and in turn likely more accurately representative of actual stories. However, being a resident adjacent to this area, this study is at a substantial risk of biases and preconceptions. Through carefully crafted questions which allow a wide

range of possible responses, I intend to mitigate the effects of my bias on the responses I capture from others.

The target sample was formed by the context of the area and the types of stories I am trying to capture. Automobility is an issue, but it is not necessarily a private or personal issue, and furthermore, it affects the entire community rather than select individuals. Therefore, a Facebook group, with the purpose of providing connections for neighbors and local residents of a single town to discuss local events and topics, seemed and proved to be an appropriate place to garner honest responses of actual substance. Within potential survey respondents present in the Facebook group for Edison, the sample was to be narrowed down further by including a survey question which asked if respondents drove regularly. Since I am aiming to capture opinions on car usage and dependency in order to address the primary research question of individuals' attitudes toward their surrounding environment, surveying drivers specifically made sense for narrowing the sample, because this environment caters to drivers. Fortunately, every respondent did drive a car, which let all of my collected data be usable.

Tools for Collecting Information From These Sources of Data

The survey was created using a Google Form template and was distributed to a local group on Facebook, that is designated purely for residents of Edison, NJ. The group required a request in order to join. Though I am not a resident of Edison specifically, I included in my join request that I attend school in Edison and that I am joining for research purposes. This transparency was provided from the start to maintain ethical obligations as a researcher (Booth 2016). The group administrators admitted me to the group and in fact one of the administrators personally filled out the survey and wished me success through the research process. This interaction with the administrator served as an initial informant (Merriam 2009) and proved to me that this Facebook group was a well-selected digital space to pose thoughtful questions to individuals who were willing to kindly answer openly. The survey proved to be the most practical use of both my time and capabilities, as well as being less demanding of the subjects of research without compromising the quality of data collected (Merriam 2009). I was able to collect a higher number of useful stories than I would have been able to by interviewing individuals one-by-one. The survey questions remained open-ended to provide useful and usable data, with the exception of the sample-defining question asking if respondents drive a car.

In total, the survey contained eleven questions. The survey asked respondents their name, then their age, in order to identify them from each other during my analysis of the responses. However, it was clearly stated and enforced that beyond that, individuals' names have been kept anonymous for privacy reasons. Following the sample-defining question, respondents were asked to describe their daily commute to work or school. Following that reflection, the question was posed of which modes of transportation are preferred. Respondents were then asked to describe their last use of public transportation, and then answered the question of their comfortability walking around town. The purpose of this structure was to first ask respondents to tell a familiar and comfortable story, which is defined as a well-posed probing question in Merriam (2009), and to then ask a question about their

opinions. In doing so, responses were much more thorough and honest than they otherwise might have been.

Analysis

“Owning a car gives Freedom to go anywhere,” said a 44-year-old survey respondent. After constructing this survey with 11 total questions and advertising it to a local Facebook group for residents of Edison, NJ, 30 responses were received. It must be stated that although 30 is an astronomically small number in proportion to the population of Edison, this number should be seen as a considerable insight into the lives of Edison residents. The sample alone cannot be fully representative of everyone, but implications and patterns can certainly be identified. The survey respondents’ ages ranged from 26 to 73 years old, however, every single respondent drove a car, answering “Yes, I drive regularly” to the only required and non-open-ended question which defined each respondent as within the sample, as mentioned previously. The rest of the open-ended questions asked about peoples’ commutes and recent traffic, opinions and preferences on public transit and on owning their own vehicle, and their perspective on Edison’s walkability. A final question asked respondents what changes or improvements they wished to see in local infrastructure. Across all questions and respondents, the most prevalent patterns were that individuals enjoyed the freedom that owning a car provides, and felt that driving is the only viable option for transportation in Edison.

Freedom and Independence

Far and away the most common pattern is the emphasis on freedom and independence, and how owning and using cars allows this. One question that was particularly telling within its responses asked which methods of transportation were preferred. Of the 30 responses to this question, 26 of them definitively chose driving a car. Common phrases in regards to this included being “in control,” having “freedom,” “independence,” “flexibility,” and traveling “as [one] please[s].” Many of the respondents also emphasized the importance of their car truly being “[their] own.” These recurring phrases show a pattern of individualism that is highly present amongst this sample. The questions were not written to ask explicitly about peoples’ ideology, but rather their preferences. This distinction is important as any of them could have chosen to only provide miniscule detail or context for their preferences. However, the majority of respondents voiced their deeper beliefs fairly openly, suggesting significant pride for their individual freedoms, as suggested in Pallagst, et. al. (2021).

People’s opinions on public transportation highlight their desires for independence and discomfort with structures which they feel diminish their freedoms (Zhang & Zhang, 2018). This response to the previously mentioned question about travel preferences noted the lack of freedom of public transit: “I prefer driving as opposed to public transportation. It’s more comfortable, and I have total control over where I am going.” This answer clearly displays how from the perspective of a typical commuter, utilizing public transportation means compromising one’s independence and freedom of mobility. Another question asked respondents specifically to describe their most recent experience with public transportation. Almost all respondents wrote that they used trains to go to New York City, but none described any sort of usage locally. The opinions on their experiences were mixed across respondents. Many described “very pleasant experiences,” particularly on trains. Those

who spoke more negatively had recurring phrases of “dirty,” “uncomfortable,” and “crowded”. Others went on to speak more vividly, “NJ Transit is not as bad as the NY trains due to a lot more homelessness, fear of random people getting violent or out of character, and just not as sanitary.” Another individual put, “Last time I used a bus was a year ago, I used it to go to the AC boardwalk from my hotel. My experience wasn’t very good, the bus was full of drunks asking for money constantly.” Across all of these negative responses, public transportation experiences are associated with uncomfortable encounters with these “out of character” people, who could most commonly be characterized as lower-income or homeless. This distinct association reflects stigmas and stereotypes assigned to public transportation based in classist rhetoric driven by the self-centered nature of American capitalist individualism (Salvino et. al. 2018).

A more direct question within the survey asked specifically how respondents felt about owning their own vehicle. The answers were overwhelmingly positive, with essentially all respondents expressing confidence and pride due to their ownership of cars. The most prevalent themes were related to independence and freedom, with these two words directly appearing in around half the responses. One answer which describes these sentiments said, “Owning a car provides independence. You are free to come and go as you please. You are not dependent on a schedule that may not work for you.” This response is purely centered around the individual - the respondent takes existing structures, in this case being a transportation schedule, and denies credibility to it by implying that it is ineffective at serving people adequately, with car ownership being the only way to achieve real freedom. Another response is a key example of American individualism, which states, “I feel proud to own both of my cars and not needing to worry about how I will make it to work to make ends meet. A good work ethic pays off in numerous ways.” This response is a textbook definition of the American Dream, and the response’s context displays a strong relationship between American ideology and Car Culture. Based on the response, owning vehicles is synonymous with respectable, strong work ethic, the peak of valued ideals in American society.

These examples of driving being the desired mode of transportation based on the provided freedoms suggest an answer to the first research question. The built environment around these individuals is a car-based, automobility-perpetuating suburb (Filion 2018). The opinions and attitudes of the residents reflect their environment; there is a heavy presence of Car Culture (Pallagst et. al. 2021), allowing the local infrastructure to continuously remain car-centered, since it provides freedom, or as one respondent put it: “I own a car, and that represents independence.” This 61-year-old respondent would go on to say, “I can’t imagine living in a town like Edison without one.” This perspective suggests a concept (Hatami & Thill, 2022) that is reflected in the next section, which is the need for owning a car.

Lacking Suitable Alternatives

Car ownership is not just a freeing choice, but also a requirement to live and work adequately in this area. About a third of the responses expressed that owning a car was a necessity in the area. This concept of car ownership being a necessity suggests that the freedom granted by driving is only

a slight freedom, trapped within structures that prevent the efficacy of alternative modes of transport (Hatami & Thill, 2022).

One reason for this necessity for driving is the poor walkability resulting from the city planning culture in Edison, expressed by just over half of the survey respondents. One question from the survey asked, “How comfortable do you feel walking to get around town?” The question received, among others, this answer from a 73-year-old respondent, “Walking? I walk for pleasure daily but there is really nothing you can walk to easily in Edison unless you drive, park, then walk.” Though this respondent is an elderly individual, who may struggle walking long distances, another respondent who was 32 years old echoed similar sentiments, saying, “Not comfortable as everything isn’t as close and definitely feels more than a 20 minute walk to a local place.” For further context, this individual was one of the few respondents who utilizes public transportation daily, commuting into the highly walkable New York City. Although other respondents spoke more favorably about the area’s walkability, the majority of them were referencing Metuchen, a small township within Edison’s borders but outside of its municipal jurisdiction. In regards to Edison itself, one respondent aptly put, “There is no center of town, so walking anywhere is just not practical.” Walkability is a crucial factor in reducing car dependence in cities and suburbs (Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021). Edison does lack a distinct center of town, and most of its roads have poorly maintained sidewalks, if any. It duly lacks a downtown, and its parks and other greenways are accompanied by parking lots and are situated near high-speed roads, for example Lake Papaiani Park right off of New Jersey Highway 27. Without walking being a viable option to get around, cars become a clear necessity. Even if it is in some places, the general attitude of residents is that it is not, so regardless, cars are the dominant form of transportation.

Edison, NJ is home to the Edison station of NJ Transit, which runs rail services from New York City to Trenton with a number of stops in between on the Northeast Corridor line. There are also stations in Iselin and Metuchen that are in accessible proximity to Edison on the same rail line. However, these stations do not provide transportation locally within the township and bus services in Edison are limited, once again being a major factor necessitating automobility. When asked on preferred methods of transportation in the survey, one respondent said, “Prefer train. But need flexibility of car. No trains in area of my office.” This simple answer represents the key issue with public transit infrastructure in the United States. It simply is not present in enough spaces (Dovey et. al. 2017). Without accessible stations near populated cities, towns, and both residential and industrial hubs, there become less and less individuals inclined to utilize public transportation. The lack of normalized use of public transit contributes to disdain for the service and further perpetuates Car Culture (Salvino et. al. 2018).

When considering alternative options to driving, walking or public transportation might not even be considered. One respondent described the necessity of owning a car as opposed to the costly nature of rideshare services, saying, “For me, having a car is a necessity I sometimes forget to be grateful. Though it’s not cheap, especially with insurance, it’s much better than constantly paying for Lyft and Ubers to get around.” This answer is a quintessential example of Car Culture (Zhang & Zhang, 2018). This respondent would much rather pay significantly more money to be independent than have to rely on rideshare services. This is not an uncommon take, on the contrary, almost all

other respondents have outlined similar views, and existing statistics (*Cars still dominate the American commute*, 2022) certainly back this up on a national scale. Furthermore, rideshare services such as Uber and Lyft are only an alternative to driving for the individual. Someone still has to own, drive, and maintain those vehicles, and they are still regular cars. Unlike buses, which allow many passengers on fixed routes, a rideshare service has the same effect on traffic and the environment as driving your car, and simply offers one or a handful of people conditional convenience. These services being seen as an alternative to driving highlight how actually differing modes of transportation are ineffective, and the only suitable alternative is not that alternative at all.

These examples of car use being the necessary and only viable option for driving help to answer the second research question, of how suburban infrastructure patterns necessitate use of consumer automobiles. Cars are needed for basic commutes across suburbs when destinations are too great a distance to walk to, as well as if sidewalks are poorly maintained, or not even present (Pallagst et. al. 2021). Cars are needed when public transportation options do not adequately provide services to well-trafficked areas, such as places of work, and if schedules and availability are not aligned with peoples' needs (Zhang & Zhang, 2018). Cars are needed to the degree that if you are not driving, you are still likely traveling via a car; just someone else's.

Tying Patterns Together

Do individuals' attitudes toward car ownership reflect the environment and infrastructure around them? According to the 30 collected responses to the survey, the answer would have to be yes. In a built environment which prioritizes and necessitates cars (Zhang & Zhang, 2018), the residents and community in the area prefer driving due to its convenience and freedom, dislike public transportation due to socioeconomic stigma (Salvino et. al. 2018), and feel strongly proud of their car ownership. This pride contributes to, either consciously or not, a perpetuation of their car-centered world.

How do suburban infrastructure patterns necessitate use of consumer automobiles? According to the personal perspectives captured in the survey, poor walkability as a result of suburban sprawl (Hatami & Thill, 2022), distinctly lacking adequate public transportation access (Dovey et. al. 2017, Guerra & Cervero, 2011), and alternative options ultimately still contributing to car culture (Zhang & Zhang, 2018), lead to driving a personal vehicle being the primary, most popular, and in most cases the only viable option for all transportation needs. Although it is theoretically possible to not take one's car everywhere, it is simply the less sensible thing to do based on the infrastructure in Edison, NJ, a situation that is likely the case in most other suburbs across the United States.

With these questions addressed, there is evidently a very clear relationship between personal beliefs in a given location and the built environment of that location. By calling attention to and examining how certain individuals feel about Car Culture and infrastructure, this relationship can be more closely defined and understood than before. Infrastructure is designed to serve the population, and if the population appreciates aspects in their lifestyles which allow poor infrastructure patterns,

those patterns will remain present and will continue to be found as car-centric, congested, and environmentally unfriendly infrastructure is developed further.

Conclusion

From the analysis of the data collected, it can be reasonably concluded that personal ideologies about car ownership *do* reflect the built environment. The responses from the survey effectively illustrate this fact in near-unison. Respondents' showed a repeated emphasis on the freedom and pride they feel from owning and driving their own cars, and enjoyment of an individualistic lifestyle. This aligns with the car-centered infrastructure, or automobility, present within the built environment of Edison that perpetuates such a lifestyle (Pallagst et. al. 2021, Soliz 2021).

Car use is necessitated in suburban spaces through the inefficient spacing of suburban sprawl and a lack of suitable alternatives in the forms of walkability or public transportation. The survey made clear peoples' reservations about walking and public transportation as primary methods of mobility, due to lack of comfort, convenience, and safety. With these factors, the only suitable option would be to drive a car (Dovey et. al. 2017, Talal et. al. 2022).

These answers show us the significance of this problem - a tangible and distinct connection between people and their infrastructure. This problem affects both people as individuals through their options and choices as drivers, and as a community through the conditions of their surrounding environment. While obtaining a small sample of drivers cannot tell us definitively the experiences of an entire population, it can still tell us about these select drivers' experiences, particularly in a space where most people share many common experiences (Chartoudinou 2022, Pallagst et. al. 2021).

Implications

These conclusions imply a significant impact on the lives of everyday people. Mainly, the infrastructure in a given area will affect how people make choices and feel about those choices. To be specific for the case of Edison, the car-centered area leads to a population of people who are proud to own and drive cars. These decisions that people make are unconsciously affected by their environmental conditions and may contribute to financial hardships in the form of car maintenance and time lost due to inefficient mobility (Fillion 2018, Hatami & Thill 2022).

For researchers who are studying automobility and urban planning, this study implies a correlating relationship between culture and infrastructure. This study suggests that how people feel about transportation may directly reflect in how infrastructure is developed around them, and can contribute to how infrastructure continues to be developed through public policy endorsed by advocacy from the community (Loorbach 2022). Examples of this could be seen in the Edison Residents Facebook Group, where complaints and suggestions about roads and other infrastructure are common. This understanding of public influence can contribute to further research about automobility and can strengthen perspectives toward positive change in communities (Loorbach 2022).

As this study focuses primarily on individuals' attitudes toward infrastructure, a future study should examine the political systems that create and enforce automobility and, concretely, what

methods of advocacy and local policy can be utilized to enact tangible change toward sustainable cities and suburbs (Bass & Livingston 2019, Loorbach 2022, Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki 2021, Talal et. al. 2022).

Next Steps

Car dependency poses an impracticality onto built environments, while also posing financial and environmental problems for both immediate residents and broader communities (Pallagst et. al. 2021, Talal et. al. 2022). With personal attitudes being so influential upon the built environment, a logical next step would be to change the narrative about alternative modes of transportation such as walking, cycling, and public transportation to affect how suburban areas are developed in the future. Through advocacy and continued conversations, residents of a community such as Edison can enact changes in public policy and zoning regulations to create more walkable and accessible spaces (Loorbach 2022, Talal et. al. 2022). As previously mentioned, a dedicated future study to understand an effective method to enact these steps could assist in making them significantly more achievable.

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